

Speculation on Maxwell's EM Equations, Special Relativity and Quantum Mechanics

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Basic special relativity ($-E^2 + p \cdot p / c^2 = -m_0^2 c^2$) allows for two solutions, a particle with rest mass m_0 and a photon ($m_0=0$). In (1), we argued that the underlying feature of a particle/photon is an inherent force. It is through this force that energy may be transferred. Thus, E , p (energy and momentum) do not seem to have much meaning unless there is an accompanying inherent force. We argue that for a particle with rest mass, this inherent force is m_0 (inertia), and E and p are proportional to this inherent force. For a photon, which always moves with speed c in a vacuum, matters are more complicated. In (1), we postulated an inherent force (electric field E) together with an accompanying second vector B (magnetic field) also linked to force. The two forces are needed to create a momentum density, because both E and B are oscillatory and take on positive and negative values, while momentum density has only one sign. In (1), we argued that given two inherent force related vectors E and B , one may create rotational scalars $E \cdot E$ and $B \cdot B$ for energy density and $E \times B$ for momentum density.

In this note, we argue that one may establish a set of differential equations for the photon solution. These, however, do not describe a full charge-current Maxwell's em set of equations. We argue that in order to establish the notion of charge, one may point out that a photon may be trapped within a particle with rest mass. This means that E and B of the photon must somehow be able to interact with a E and B (or at least E) inside m_0 . In this case, however, E and B are not linked with a moving object (speed c), but with a stationary object and so we postulate the notion of a number q linked to E , just as m_0 , inertia, represents a force. With this idea, one may generalize the differential equations linked to the photon to include sources (q and a moving q) and obtain Maxwell's EM equations. This further leads to the notion that if one has a $-q$ and $+q$ superimposed, overall q would disappear and one would have a two photon solution (to conserve momentum). Thus, mathematically, the notion of matter-anti-matter seems to be present.

Special Relativity and Quantum Mechanics

Basic special relativity

$$-E^2 + c^2 p \cdot p = -m_0^2 c^4 \quad ((1))$$

gives rise to two solutions, one for $m_0 > 0$ and one for $m_0 = 0$ (photon).

We have argued in previous notes (like (1)), that the central concept of a particle is an inherent force, which is needed to allow for the energy E in special relativity (as well as momentum) to be transferred in an interaction. If there is no inherent force, it is not clear what E and p mean. For a particle with rest mass m_0 , we argue that this is proportional to the inherent force (inertia) as well as being proportional to E and p . For a photon which may only move at c (in a vacuum), we

argue that the inherent force is the essence of the photon and so should be a function of $-Et+px$. The question then becomes: What is the suitable function?

Quantum Mechanical Probability Linked to Inherent Force

Given the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et+px \quad ((2))$$

we note that x,t and $x+hbar/p$ and $t+hbar/E$ yield the same solution. We suggest that this implies that the inherent force interacts probabilistically at different x,t points even though the center-of-mass moves as $x=vt$ for a particle with rest mass. This leads to the notion of a complex probability which ensures the conservation of energy and momentum:

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((3))$$

In the case of the photon, we introduced a vector force and so it should behave as:

$$\cos(-Et+px) \quad ((4))$$

((4)) may be negative or positive at different x,t , but momentum density must have one sign. We thus introduce a second inherent force related vector B such that

$E \cdot E$ and $B \cdot B$ represent E density terms and $E \times B$, a momentum density term ((5))

Maxwell's Equations for a Photon

Given ((5)) and the notion of the cross-product, we suggest that one may establish a set of math equations which yield ((4)) and

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} (.5e_0 E \cdot E + .5/u_0 B \cdot B) + \text{grad dot } 1/u_0 (E \times B) = 0 \quad ((5))$$

We call ((5)) a continuity equation for a photon (and introduce $.5, e_0, u_0$ as these constants appear in the Maxwell formalism. Here, they are constant which we introduce.)

We suggest that one should have partial differential equations involving $\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial}$, grad partial , grad dot and grad x for mathematical completeness. One must obtain an equation for E yielding $\cos(-Et+px)$ and also ((5)).

One may see that the set of equations

$$\text{Grad dot } B = 0 \quad \text{grad dot } E = 0 \quad \frac{dE}{dt} \text{partial} = C_1 \text{grad x } B \quad \frac{dB}{dt} \text{partial} = C_2 \text{grad x } E \quad ((6))$$

satisfy these conditions. Given that one already has the solution ((4)) from probability considerations and energy and momentum density from dot and cross product considerations, one might consider that ((6)) is overkill, but we try to establish these equations due a feature which we discuss in the next section.

The Concept of Charge

We noted that basic special relativity allows for a rest mass particle and a photon as solutions. The photon always moves with speed c in a vacuum. We argue, however, that a photon may be trapped (bouncing back and forth) within a rest mass. In such a case, it adds no extra momentum on average, but does add extra energy which may be considered rest mass. (A particle with rest mass would do the same.) The point we make is that if the photon interacts through its inherent force (the electric field and associated B), then these same forces should exist within the rest mass as well. In other words, one cannot take it for granted that an interaction occurs unless the appropriate forces are present. In the case of the rest mass, m_0 , however, the E and B inside are linked with a stationary object m_0 and not a photon moving at speed c . For a stationary object, we suggest that there should be a number q linked with the electric field. This number should also somehow be linked to the B field. We thus suggest that the set of equations ((6)) may be modified to include q . We suggest that for m_0 which is at rest, there is one parameter m_0 and one force. Following this analogy, q should perhaps pertain to only one kind of force as well, perhaps the electric field E . B might then be linked to q multiplied by a velocity. In other words, the density associated with q might act like a 4-vector giving rise to q -density and q -current (like a q momentum). We realize that these are rather strong assumptions, but they seem to be consistent with the treatment of m_0 . In such a case, one might suggest:

$$\text{Grad dot } E = q\text{-density}/\epsilon_0 \quad \text{grad dot } B = 0 \quad dB/dt \text{ partial} = \text{grad} \times E$$

$$dE/dt \text{ partial} + \mu_0 q\text{-density} * v = \text{grad} \times B \quad ((7))$$

We note that the above approach is based largely on math, but Maxwell's original derivation of his em equations was also based on a mathematical description of experimental results.

The Possibility of Anti-Matter

We note that the photon solution of ((7)) involves setting q and hence q -density and q -density * v to 0. An alternative approach is to have a $+q$ and $-q$ superimposed so that overall q and q current disappear, if in fact it is possible to have a $+q$ and $-q$. If it is possible, then such a q and $-q$ is equivalent mathematically to two photons (to conserve momentum). As a result, the notion of a photon linked to E, B and a q , q -density and q -current linked also to E and B suggests that these two different scenarios could be interchangeable, i.e. one could have matter $-q$ and antimatter $-q$ convert into two photons.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that basic special relativity describes two kinds of particles, one with rest mass $m_0 > 0$ and the other, a photon, with $m_0 = 0$. Both of these particles are associated with energy E and momentum p which is conserved. We suggest, however, that in order for E and p to make physical sense, each particle must have an inherent force. For a particle with rest mass, m_0 (inertia) is proportional to the inherent force, while for a photon, we postulate in (1) a force which moves as a function of $-Et+px$ and creates the energy and momentum density. We find from special relativity that the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ implies that x, t and $x+h\bar{v}/p$, $t+h\bar{v}/E$ yield the same value and so we argued in (1) that the inherent force strikes in a probabilistic manner.

This means that the inherent force for a photon (which we call electric field E_I) should behave as $\cos(-Et+px)$ and that one requires a second force related vector B which also behaves as $\cos(-Et+px)$ in order to create a momentum density $E_I \times B$ which has the same sign. The energy density is then linked with $E_I \cdot E_I$ and $B \cdot B$. This leads to a continuity type equation for a photon: $d/dt \text{ partial } (.5\epsilon_0 E_I \cdot E_I + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B) + 1/\mu_0 \text{ grad } \cdot (E_I \times B) = 0$. We suggest that one may write a set of partial differential equations ((6)) which describe E_I and B , but these are not overly interesting as one knows the form $\cos(-Et+px) e_j$ (where motion is in the x direction and e_j a unit vector in the y direction) from probability.

Now, a photon may be trapped in a rest mass object. This means that E_I and B , or at least E_I , must exist within m_0 otherwise the photon would not be able to interact. We argue that given that m_0 is constant due to a rest frame, there should exist a second parameter which we call q which accounts for E_I inside m_0 . E_I in the photon behaves as $\cos(-Et+px) e_j$. As a result we suggest that ((6)) may be generalized to account for both a photon and a rest mass particle with q , q -density and q -density $\cdot v$ (4-vector). This combination then gives rise to the full Maxwell electromagnetic equations.

We further suggest that given the two scenarios: photon and q based particle within the same set of differential equations, that if one had a $+q$ and $-q$ superimposed, then this would be like a no source situation and should be equivalent to two photons (for momentum conservation). This would then be a math description of matter-antimatter.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on the Photon Momentum and Electric Field (preprint, zenodo, 2026)